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Determination of forming limit curve in two-layer metallic sheets using the finite element simulation

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Abstract

Forming limit curve (FLC) is a suitable method in order to determine the metallic sheets formability. The purpose of present research is to expose a simulation-based approach to predict the forming limit curve in two-layer metallic sheets. In this paper, the formability of two-layer (AA3004-ST12) metallic sheets, with an aluminum inner layer (in contact with the punch) and a steel outer layer (in contact with the die) was numerically investigated. Two distinct criteria, including the acceleration (i.e. the second time derivatives) of thickness, and major strain extracted from the strain history information of FE software, were applied to determine the commencement of local necking in forming limit curves. It shows that the localized necking starts when the acceleration of the thickness or major strain, is maximized. The published experimental results for AA3004/ST12 two-layer metallic sheets were employed in order to evaluate the simulation results. It is shown that the presented methods are noticeably aligned with the published experimental data. By the grace of present methods, the effects of some process parameters on the FLC have been investigated. It is shown that process parameters such as thickness and lay-up of each layer will have significant influences on FLC of two-layer metallic sheets.

Keywords: Two-layer metallic sheet, Forming limit curve, FEM

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1 Introduction

Two-layer metallic sheets have become as a useful solution to produce multi-functional products. Generally in two-layer metallic sheets, by combination of different materials could result in remarkable characteristics such as enhancing the formability of low formable component, improving the corrosion and wear resistance and ultimately reducing weight and cost of manufactured products. These kinds of sheets can be used in lots of industrial applications [1-4]. Forming limit curves (FLCs) are applied to predict the formability of metallic sheets. Regarding find the FLC experimentally, some sheet metal specimens of constant length and variable width were subjected to different strain conditions using a hemispherical punch. After the presentation of the forming limit curves concept by Keeler and Backofen [5] and then Goodwin [6], many researchers tried to develop some models for determination of FLCs. Ito et al. [7] determined the forming limit curve of sheet metal theoretically by the mean of three-dimensional mode analysis. The numerical results showed that the strain limit determined using this method, provided upper limits for any linear strain-path directions. Zimniak [8] determined the forming limit diagram (FLD) by perturbation theory using the FEM simulations. His study demonstrated that the modification of the perturbation theory with a new stress-strain relationship and six-component Barlat yield criterion will provide a suitable estimation of the onset of localized necking to determine the forming limit curve. Butuc et al. [9] focused on the forming limit curves using a new general code to predict the forming limit strains. They used the Yld96 criterion to describe the shape of the yield locus then observed a good correlation between the computed limit strains and the experimental FLCs. Aghaie-Khafri and Mahmudi [10] presented an analytical method to determine the forming limit curves obtained during sheet metal forming processes for sheets with planar isotropy. Campos et al. [11] determined the forming limit curve for the AISI 304 stainless

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steel using the Marciniak Kuczynski (M–K) method. Safikhani et al. [12] presented the forming limit curves both in strain and stress spaces using the strain gradient theory of plasticity in conjunction with M–K model. Zhang et al. [13] demonstrated a suitable necking criterion to determine FLCs of aluminum alloys. Rezaee-Bazzaz et al. [14] calculated the FLCs, using the analysis suggested by Jones and Gillis (JG). They found that although the method reasonably determined the influence of material parameters, but computed FLCs were higher than the experimental forming limit curves. Albakri et al. [15] showed a novel hybrid numerical/experimental approach that could be applied to make forming limit curve, beneath the specified strain rate loading paths in sheet metal forming processes. For most of sheet materials under complex loading processes used in industry, strong Bauschinger effect is observed, and the material hardening behavior tends to be anisotropic. Therefore, Ji He et al. [16] tried to understand and evaluate such anisotropic hardening effect on the forming limit prediction, in stretch-bending condition. They predicted the “bending-ratio-dependent” phenomenon in forming limit curve in both stress/strain space with the proposed method. Their analysis demonstrated that the Bauschinger effect provides positive effect to make delay the necking instability, resulting in higher formability for sheet metals under stretch-bending. Mamusi et al. [17] determined the forming limit curve of laser-welded low carbon steel (ST12 and ST14) blanks both experimentally and numerically using a new simulation-based approach. Silva et al. [18] developed hole-flanging by incremental sheet forming as an innovative metal forming technology for flexible small batch-production of cylindrical or conical flanges in blanks with pre-cut holes. The process was seen as an alternative to hole-flanging by conventional press-working due to significant cost savings through the replacement of complex press-tools by simple dieless forming apparatuses and to widespread belief that the limiting forming ratio of

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hole-flanging by incremental sheet forming was always higher than that of hole-flanging by conventional press-working. They focused on the aforementioned assumption and investigated the influence of material failure by necking and fracture on the limiting forming ratio. The experimental work was performed in a CNC machining center and a hydraulic press equipped with apparatuses for multi-stage single point incremental forming and conventional press-tooling, and the strain loading paths resulting from each forming process were determined by circle grid analysis. Results in Aluminium AA1050-H111 and Titanium (grade 2) blanks demonstrated that there were process operating conditions leading to higher limiting forming ratio of hole-flanging by conventional press-working than by incremental sheet forming due to closeness of the forming limit curve and fracture forming limit line in the principal strain space. Zhang et al. [19] used the Marciniak–Kuczynski method with Barlat's 1989 anisotropic yield surface to obtain forming limit diagrams and study the effect of normal stress and material anisotropy. Their analysis showed that normal stress increased the forming limit both in strain and stress spaces.

The earliest research on multi-layer materials was carried out by Semiatin and Piehler [20]. Yoshida and Hino [21] investigated the forming limit of sheet metal laminates under biaxial stress conditions. A criterion of localized necking for the laminates, in the negative strain-ratio condition ($\beta = \epsilon_2 / \epsilon_1 \leq 0$, ϵ_1 : major strain and ϵ_2 : minor strain), was derived based on Hill's theory of localized necking. For biaxial stretching ($\beta = \epsilon_2 / \epsilon_1 > 0$), a modified M-K model was used. The calculated FLD were compared with the corresponding experimental results determined by punch-stretching experiments on two- and three-ply stainless steel-clad aluminum sheets. Both in the analytical predictions and the experimental observations, the FLDs of the laminates situated between those of their component sheet metals. The effect of prestrain generated in the roll-

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bonding process on the formability was discussed. Weiss et al. [22] studied the influence of temperature on the forming behavior of an aluminum/polypropylene/aluminum (APA) sandwich sheet. Shear and tensile tests were performed to determine the mechanical properties of the laminate and the component materials as a function of process temperature. The FLD of the laminate was established for two different temperatures, and its springback behavior was examined in four-point bend and channel-bend tests. Cup forming tests were performed at various test temperatures to determine the limiting drawing ratio (LDR) and the tendency for wrinkling at these temperatures. Although there was only a minor influence of temperature on the mechanical properties and the FLD values of the laminate, the bend test results revealed that springback could be reduced by forming at higher temperature. The decreasing strength of the core material with rising process temperature led to an increased tendency of the laminate to wrinkle in the heated cup drawing tests. Tseng et al. [23] investigated the forming limits of clad metal sheets with different thickness combinations (e.g., A1050 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 mm/C1100 1.0 mm) via forming limits test (punch stretching tests). The true stress–strain curves of Al/Cu clad metal sheets were obtained through tensile tests. Using the experimental forming limit diagrams and the stress–strain curves, the fracture prediction of clad metal sheets were simulated by finite element analysis. Moreover, deep drawing tests were carried out to compare the experimental with the numerical results. These results could verify the accuracy of finite element model. Finally, significant differences in formability were found, and comparisons of the fracture prediction of clad metals with different initial thickness ratios were analyzed both numerically and experimentally. Liu et al. [24] developed an AA5052/polyethylene/AA5052 sandwich sheet and investigated its formability. Their study demonstrated that: AA5052/polyethylene/AA5052 sandwich sheet had better formability than monolithic AA5052 sheet. Aghchai et al. [25]

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investigated the effects of material properties of each component of two-layer sheets such as strain rate sensitivity coefficient, strain hardening exponent, grain size and stiffness coefficient on the FLC of two-layer sheets with the M–K method which was then verified by an experimental approach. Their study showed that the forming limits of two-layer sheet situated between the forming limits of its own components depend on their material properties.

Although the fracture occurs by previous necking in many sheet metal forming processes, there are also some processes where fracture can be developed regardless of previous necking [26-29]. This research is limited in situations where necking occurs before failure by fracture.

In this research, two different numerical models were used to determine the formability of two-layer metallic sheets. These methods contain: (1) Acceleration of the major strain ($\frac{d^2\varepsilon_{11}}{dt^2}$) and (2) Acceleration of the thickness strain ($\frac{d^2\varepsilon_{33}}{dt^2}$) to predict the forming limit of two-layer sheets. These two criteria were employed for the first time to determine the FLCs of two-layer metallic sheets. The published experimental test results were applied to validate the results of the proposed methods. Furthermore, the influences of process parameters on the FLC of two-layer metallic sheets were investigated through numerical simulations.

2 Numerical modeling

The biaxial stretch-forming test was simulated in three-dimensional (3D) using ABAQUS/Explicit FE software [30] to estimate the formability of the AA3004/ST12 two-layer metallic sheets. All the analysis used an explicit finite element approach. Figure 1 shows the geometrical setup which was simulated in FE software. In this simulation, the element size of

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blanks was set to 2.1 mm (e.g., an 80mm sample contained 3920 elements based on the selected element size). The coefficients of friction between different contacting surfaces are presented in Table 1 [23, 31].

Figure 1: Schematic of die, punch and blank holder (all dimensions are in mm)

Table 1: Coefficient of friction between contact surfaces [23, 31]

Surface of contact	Coefficient of friction
Between blank & punch surface	0.08
Between blank & blank holder surface	0.1
Between blank & die surface	0.1

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Punch, die, and blank holder were modeled as an analytical rigid part because their deformations are negligible. Moreover, the blanks were modeled as a deformable part by composite shell elements (four nodes, reduced integration elements, ABAQUS type S4R). The materials were used in the power hardening law for each layer. The FEM model included of a punch, blank holder, die and the blank as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Modeling in ABAQUS software

This analysis was simulated in three steps. In first step, the blank holder moved down in the z-direction and deformed the sheet metal sample into the draw bead. The hemispherical punch and die were fixed in this step. The punch, die, and blank holder remained fixed in the second step, however, a blank holder force applied to the blank. In third step, while the boundary condition at

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second step was still in effect, the punch started to move downward in the z-direction with a numerical velocity of 1,000 mm/s.

The total thickness of ST12 and AA3004 sheets was both 2.1mm, and the two-layer sheet was made of 0.6mm ST12 and 1.5mm AA3004 sheets as it mentioned in [25]. The specimens with different geometries were simulated according to ISO 12004-2 standard [32] to obtain the forming limit curve in this study. Figure 3 shows the geometries of used specimens to obtain the FLC. Also, the mechanical properties of each layer used in this research are shown in Table 2 [25, 33]. These tensile test properties were used in the simulations.

Figure 3: The different specimens’ geometries to obtain the FLC (all the dimensions in mm)

Table 2: Material and mechanical properties of ST12 and AA3004 sheets from tensile tests [25, 33]

Material	Specific gravity, ρ (Kg/m ³)	Strain hardening exponent, n	Strength coefficient, K (MPa)	Young Module, E (GPa)	Yield Strength, σ_y (MPa)	Ultimate Strength, σ_{ult} (MPa)	Uniform elongation, %
ST12	7800	0.25	544	200	174	305	30
AA3004	2720	0.25	302	70	110	175	8

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The influences of process parameters such as thickness of each layer and also their lay-up were studied by FE simulations.

2.1. Analytical necking criterion

Selecting appropriate necking criteria is important to determine the onset of localized necking in sheet metal forming operations (Figure 4). As mentioned earlier, in this research two different necking criteria, namely the *acceleration of the major strain* and the *acceleration of the thickness strain* were used to detect the onset of necking.

Figure 4: Typical FEM results depicting the onset of necking in a deformed specimen

Two new criteria determining the onset of localized necking in two-layer metallic sheets were proposed to obtain the limit strains of each strain path and subsequently the FLC. The procedure for computing the limit strain was to process the history of major strain and thickness strain by

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taking the 2nd order of derivative. The limit strain for a given strain path was achieved at maximum value of strain acceleration. The processing of major and thickness strains and accelerations have been presented in detail in sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2. Temporal strain data was collected from FE simulations of hemispherical punch tests through particular strain paths. This process was repeated for all specimen geometries to obtain a locus of the limit strains, i.e., FLC for given material.

2.1.1. The acceleration of the major strain criterion

By utilizing this method, necking time of a particular specimen can be predicted. To predict the FLC numerically, it is vital to determine the location of the point on the specimen where necking occurs. It was deduced that by means of evaluation of major strain and its acceleration in time, it would be possible to determine the necking time of material. This criterion was first presented by Situ [34] which is based on the acceleration (or second derivative) of the major strain in the blank and is defined as follow:

$$\ddot{\varepsilon}_{11} = (d^2 \varepsilon_{11}) / (dt^2) \quad (1)$$

in which ε_{11} is the major strain.

First of all, the localized necking area was detected. Localized necking area can be physically identified as an unstable local reduction in the sheet thickness in a region with a size of the order of sheet thickness. After beginning the necking process, all the strains in sheet become concentrated in this particular region. The strain rates in areas far from the necking zone, decrease gradually and vanish at last. Figure 5 demonstrates the time evaluation of the major strain in a stretch-bending test at various aligned points along a section perpendicular to the groove. The strain level of some points (A and B) increases monotonically until fracture, while

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other points (C, D, and E) cease to strain and even undergo some elastic unloading just before failure. The first set of points is clearly located in the region of instability, and the second set of points is located in regions adjacent to the necking zone. This pattern is a characteristic of the process of strain localization during the development of instability. Therefore, the necking zone width can be determined as shown in Figure 5 [35, 36].

Figure 5: The time evaluation of the major strain at various aligned points along a section perpendicular to the groove in a simulation to detect the necking region

The necking time was determined from an analysis of strain history by extraction 2nd order of derivative of major strain for a series of aligned points at critical side of two-layer metallic sheets (i.e., steel layer) along a section perpendicular to the groove. The time in which the acceleration of major strain reaches its maximum magnitude, was considered as the onset of localized

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necking [34]. The element at the critical side of two-layer metallic sheet, in which the maximum magnitude of major strain acceleration first appears in the necking area, was assumed as the element where the onset of necking starts. At end of the simulation, the major strain history was extracted from the output file of the FE model and its second derivative was then plotted (Figure

6). The time of necking ($t_{necking}$) was determined from the second derivative curve.

Figure 6: Acceleration of the major strain history information to detect the onset of necking

The major and minor strains at point A at the necking time ($t_{necking}$) were collected from the ABAQUS result file, and were put into FLC (Figure 7). This procedure was repeatedly performed for all the simulated specimen geometries of each analyzed materials.

Figure 7: Major strain and minor strain at the necking time to produce the FLC

2.1.2. The acceleration of the thickness strain criterion

Material narrowing can be a criterion for necking prediction [37, 38]. The procedure to predict the forming limit curve by this criterion is as same as that of the acceleration of the major strain criterion. The acceleration (or second derivative) of thickness strain in blank, is defined as:

$$\ddot{\varepsilon}_{33} = (d^2 \varepsilon_{33}) / (dt^2) \quad (2)$$

in which ε_{33} is the thickness strain.

These two criteria are introduced here as necking criteria in order to determine the FLC in two-layer metallic sheets for the first time.

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A comparison between the strain history of major and thickness strains is presented as Figure 8.

Also Figure 9 shows the relation of thickness strain with major strain. These Figures illustrate that there will be a linear relation between these criteria. Therefore, the maximum value of their acceleration curves happens at the same time and so the resulting FLC would be similar. Thus, it is expected that the two criteria show the same results.

Figure 8: Comparison between the strain history of major and thickness strains

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Figure 9: Linear relation between thickness strain and major strain

Strain-based forming limit curves are typically determined under linear loading conditions before onset of necking in the material. Figure 10 demonstrates that the strain path is almost linear up to the onset of necking in the FE model used in this work, which implies that the FLCs obtained in this research are acceptable.

Figure 10: Linearity of strain path before onset of necking in the simulation result

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Figure 11 shows the major strain and thickness strain distributions of a specimen with 80mm width. The strain distributions seem to be almost similar and the necking position is quite the same.

Figure 11: Strain distributions from a 80mm wide specimen: **(a)** Major strain, **(b)** Thickness strain

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3 Results and discussion

3.1. Forming limit curve verification

In order to validate the simulation-based approach proposed in the present work, the predicted FLCs were compared with the forming limit curve obtained experimentally [25]. In reference [25], a series of punch stretching tests were performed to evaluate the FLCs. The different regions of FLCs were obtained by tensile tests and stretch-forming with hemispherical punch experiments. In the experimental procedure, the aluminum side of the two-layer metallic sheet was in contact with the punch. Figure 12 shows a comparison between the predicted FLC and experimental data for AA3004 and ST12 one-layer sheets and AA3004/ST12 two-layer metallic sheets.

Figure 12: Comparison between the predicted FLC and the experimental data [25] for AA3004 and ST12 one layer sheets and AA3004/ST12 two-layer sheets

Figure 12 shows that these models are in good agreement with the published experimental data for AA3004 and ST12 one-layer sheets and AA3004/ST12 two-layer sheets.

FLD_0 is the major strain in plane strain state that results in necking. Table 3 compares experimental FLD_0 s with those from FE analysis. It could be seen that, the simulation results from various strain paths were in fairly good agreement with experimental ones.

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Table 3: Comparison of FLD₀

Component	FLD ₀ (Experiment)	FLD ₀ (FEM)
ST12, 2.1mm	0.253	0.291
AA3004, 2.1mm	0.219	0.211
ST12/AA3004, 2.1mm	0.235	0.261

3.2. Parametric study

A comprehensive parametric study was carried out and the effects of process parameters on the FLC of two-layer metallic sheets were studied. The influence of blank thickness on the FLCs (e.g., the FLCs of two-layer metallic sheets) is shown in Figure 13. As the Figure13 shows, with an enhancement in steel thickness in a constant total blank thickness, the FLC will be increased, meaning that the formability of two-layer metallic sheet will be improved. On the other hand, the FLC of the two-layer metallic sheet is better than the less formable component (e.g., the aluminum layer), thus utilizing a two-layer metallic sheet, improves the formability of a blank which has had a low formability.

Figure 13: Effect of each layer thickness on the FLCs

Figure 14 shows the important role of lay-up in formability of two-layer metallic sheets. As the Figure 14 shows, there is a decrease in the FLC when the aluminum layer is considered as outer layer (in contact with the die). This phenomenon also has been observed in limit drawing ratio (as an accepted measure of sheet metal formability) of Al/ST two layer sheet [39]. It means, when the layer with a lower formability (i.e. aluminum layer) is in contact with the punch and the layer with a higher strength is on the die side, the overall formability of blank will be improved.

Figure 14: Effect of lay-up on the FLC

Conclusions

In this paper, two numerical models were used to analyze the FLCs of two-layer metallic sheets. Besides, the effect of process parameters on formability of two-layer metallic sheet was investigated by the grace of numerical simulations that were verified with published experimental data. The following phrases are the conclusions obtained:

1. A new simulation-based method to predict the FLC of the two-layer metallic sheets was introduced and validated in comparison of its results with published experimental data.

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2. The FLC of the two-layer metallic sheet is located between the FLC of its own components individually, and its precise location depends on the thickness of each component.
3. The increase in the thickness of a layer with more formability, by assuming the total blank thickness constant, increases the formability of two-layer metallic sheet.
4. It is evident from the studies that there will be an increase in FLC, when the layer with less formability is in contact with the punch.

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Appendix I: Notation

FLC	Forming limit curve
FLD	Forming limit diagram
FLD ₀	Major strain in plane strain state
K (MPa)	Strength coefficient
n	Strain hardening exponent
m	Strain rate sensitivity coefficient
ν	Poisson’s ratio
r	Anisotropic parameter
\bar{r}	Average anisotropic parameter
\mathcal{E}	True strain
\mathcal{E}_1	Major strain
\mathcal{E}_2	Minor strain
\mathcal{E}_3	Thickness strain
β	In-plane principal strain ratio
Length	l
Width	w